

Resonance Evaluation of ^{177}Hf and Application to the TEX-Hf Benchmark

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ABSTRACT

Accurate nuclear data for hafnium isotopes are essential for reactor applications that involve control rods, neutron absorbers, and shielding components. Among naturally occurring isotopes, ^{177}Hf plays an important role due to its resonance absorption in the thermal and epithermal energy ranges. Despite this importance, discrepancies exist among major evaluated nuclear data libraries, particularly in the resolved resonance region and in the availability of resonance parameter covariances.

This work presents a revised evaluation of the resolved resonance parameters for ^{177}Hf developed using the SAMMY code with Bayesian R-matrix analysis. A preliminary evaluation, hereafter referred to as the new evaluation, was benchmarked against International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) critical experiments from the TEX-Hf series. These experiments were specifically designed to probe hafnium cross sections in thermal, intermediate, and fast neutron spectra.

Benchmark calculations were performed using the continuous-energy (CE) KENO module in the SCALE code system, with sensitivity analyses conducted via TSUNAMI. Results are compared against predictions using ENDF/B-VIII.1. The updated evaluation shows improved agreement with experimental k_{eff} values, particularly in the intermediate energy range, and reduces systematic bias observed in earlier evaluations.

Sensitivity profiles confirm that the TEX-Hf benchmarks are highly responsive to ^{177}Hf capture and total cross sections, validating the utility of these cases for integral data testing. This study highlights the importance of updating nuclear data for hafnium isotopes and provides a pathway for further improvements, including the incorporation of experimental measurements and covariance data for both resolved and unresolved energy regions.

Keywords: resonance, evaluation, criticality, benchmark, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Hafnium plays a central role in nuclear applications due to its high neutron absorption cross section, corrosion resistance, and mechanical robustness. It is widely used in control rods, absorber plates, and emerging fuel cycle applications. Of the six stable isotopes of hafnium, ^{177}Hf is particularly relevant because of the natural abundances and capture cross sections of these isotopes. However, ^{177}Hf ($I =$

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$7/2^-$) presents challenges in resonance evaluation due to half-integer spins, which necessitate proper treatment of spin-channel effects.

The TEX-Hf (Thermal Epithermal eXperiments) benchmark is a critical experiment developed under the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) [1] to evaluate hafnium nuclear data relevant to reactor applications. The configuration employs HEU metal plates and natural hafnium, which acts as a neutron absorber and reflector rather than a true moderator, with moderation provided by polyethylene plates of varying thicknesses. This configuration was specifically designed to probe the reactivity effects of hafnium's neutron absorption and scattering characteristics, making it an ideal candidate for validating evaluated nuclear data files.

Natural hafnium comprises several isotopes, among which ^{177}Hf is of particular interest due to its significant contribution to the resonance absorption in the epithermal energy range. Table I presents the isotopic abundances, nuclear spins, thermal neutron capture cross sections at 0.0253 eV, capture resonance integrals, and Westcott factors for the hafnium isotopes [2].

Table I. Natural abundance of hafnium isotopes.

Isotope	Abundance (%)	Spin	σ_γ (barns)	I_γ (barns)	g_γ
^{174}Hf	0.16	0^+	549 ± 7	307 ± 15	–
^{176}Hf	5.26	0^+	23.5 ± 3.1	708 ± 15	1.0003
^{177}Hf	18.60	$7/2^-$	375 ± 10	7200 ± 200	1.0199
^{178}Hf	27.28	0^+	84 ± 4	1882 ± 20	1.003
^{179}Hf	13.62	$9/2^+$	41 ± 3	630 ± 30	1.003
^{180}Hf	35.08	0^+	13.4 ± 0.07	33 ± 1	–

The accurate evaluation of ^{177}Hf resonance parameters is essential in the context of control rod design, reactor safety analysis, and shielding applications.

This paper presents a revised evaluation of the resolved resonance parameters for ^{177}Hf . This evaluation was performed using the SAMMY code [3] and was based on experimental cross section capture and transmission data obtained at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute [4] and GELINA [5]. The updated library was tested against the TEX-Hf benchmark and compared with results obtained using the ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluation. The analysis demonstrates the effect of the updated ^{177}Hf evaluation on integral benchmark predictions and highlights areas for further refinement.

2. METHODOLOGY

The resonance evaluation for ^{177}Hf was performed using the SAMMY code, which applies a Bayesian R-matrix formalism to fit experimental cross section data. The evaluation focused on the resolved resonance region.

2.1. Experimental Differential Data and SAMMY Fitting

To support the resonance evaluation of ^{177}Hf , a comprehensive set of differential data was employed. These data include high-resolution time-of-flight (TOF) transmission and capture measurements.

For the low-energy range (0.01–10 eV), two total cross section datasets (Conrad [6] and Vertebny [7]) and one capture dataset (Pavlenko [8]) were employed. These data were fitted with SAMMY for energies

below 10 eV.

In the energy range of 3–1000 eV, TOF capture measurements for ^{177}Hf were performed at the GELINA facility and subsequently used in the SAMMY resonance evaluation. Two independent datasets of capture yields were obtained at flight paths of 13 m and 28 m, providing complementary resolution and statistics for the analysis. Comprehensive details of the experimental data are available in Ware et al. [9].

A set of high-resolution TOF transmission measurements was performed for a ^{177}Hf -enriched sample (74.35% enrichment) at the Columbia University Nevis synchrocyclotron using the 202.05 m flight path [10]. The data were analyzed in the energy range from 30 to 1000 eV.

The R-matrix code SAMMY was used to fit the experimental data described previously. In this study, the analysis focused on the low-energy resonance region and the energy range covering the interval from 5 to 250 eV. This energy range contains several prominent resonances that are highly relevant for applications in reactor physics and criticality safety, making accurate resonance parameter evaluation essential. Both total cross section and capture measurements were included in the fitting procedure to ensure consistency across reaction channels. The SAMMY code incorporates experimental resolution functions, background corrections, and self-shielding effects, all of which are critical for reproducing the observed resonance behavior. Initial resonance parameters were adopted from evaluated nuclear data libraries and refined through least-squares adjustment to best describe the experimental observable. The fitted results show good agreement with the measurements. The SAMMY analysis provided resonance energies, neutron widths, and radiative capture widths, along with uncertainties derived from the covariance matrix. The covariance matrix is computed as part of the Bayesian fitting procedure within SAMMY and reflects the propagated uncertainties based on experimental statistics, resolution, and model assumptions. It was not derived from external or previously evaluated data. Figure 1 shows the comparison between SAMMY calculations and the experimental data for the total and capture cross section in the 0.01–1 eV range. Figure 2 shows comparison of data listed in Ware et al. [9], capture data

Figure 1. SAMMY fitting of the total and capture cross section data below 1 eV.

at 13 m and 28 m, and total cross section listed in Liou et al. [10] in the 5–250 eV energy range. The fits shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 demonstrate the reliability of the SAMMY R-matrix approach in reproducing the measured cross section data.

In addition to the SAMMY fits, thermal values of the capture (σ_γ) and scattering (σ_s) cross sections, as well as the Westcott factors (g_γ), were calculated. The results are shown in Table II and compared with the corresponding values from ENDF/B-VIII.1. Overall, good agreement is observed for the capture cross sections and the Westcott factors. However, a significant discrepancy is found in the scattering cross section, underscoring the importance of SAMMY analysis in refining the scattering cross at thermal. Further investigation is needed to understand this difference.

Figure 2. SAMMY fitting of the total and cross section and capture yield data in the energy range of 5–250 eV.

Table II. Thermal values and Westcott factors derived from the evaluated resonance parameters.

Quantities	New Evaluation	ENDF/B-VIII.1
σ_γ (barns)	370.891	371.887
σ_s (barns)	0.0411	0.216
g_γ	1.0197	1.0198

A comparison of the capture cross section between the new ^{177}Hf resonance evaluation and ENDF/B-VIII.1 in the energy range from 200 eV to 250 eV reveals notable differences. As indicated by the blue-highlighted region in Figure 3, the new evaluation introduces additional resonance structures around 200–210 eV that are not present in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluation. These newly identified features reflect improved fitting to both total and capture cross section data, and highlight the sensitivity of the SAMMY-based analysis in resolving previously unobserved resonance structures in this energy region. It is observed that the ENDF/B-VIII.1 resonances are not well aligned with those in the new evaluation. However, the new evaluation is based on high-resolution transmission data measured at Columbia University’s Nevis synchrocyclotron using a 202.05-meter [10] flight path, which provides reliable determination of resonance positions.

2.2. AMPX Processing for SCALE/KENO Calculations

Focus of this section is the use of the AMPX code to generate libraries tailored for the SCALE code system; particular emphasis was given to continuous-energy KENO calculations. The workflow includes reading evaluated data, performing Doppler broadening, resonance reconstruction, probability table generation, and producing cross section formats optimized for Monte Carlo transport. Special attention is given to the treatment of resonance parameters and the generation of probability tables, which are critical for accurate continuous-energy simulations in KENO. The ^{177}Hf JEFF-4.0 evaluation was used as the template into which the new resonance parameters were incorporated for the energy range from 1×10^{-5} eV to 1 keV. The choice of JEFF-4.0 was motivated by the fact that its representation of the unresolved resonance and higher-energy regions has demonstrated better overall performance compared with alternative evaluations. Cross section libraries were generated for both the new ^{177}Hf evaluation and ENDF/B-VIII.1 in a format suitable for continuous-energy calculations with the KENO Monte Carlo code in the SCALE system. Preparing libraries that are directly usable in KENO allows the effect of the new resonance evaluation to be assessed via benchmark calculations, criticality safety

Figure 3. Comparison of ^{177}Hf Capture Cross Sections Between the New Evaluation and ENDF/B-VIII.1 in the 200–250 eV Range.

studies, and reactor physics applications, providing a direct link between nuclear data evaluation and practical analysis.

3. TEX-HF BENCHMARK EXPERIMENTS

The TEX-Hf benchmark series was developed to support the validation of nuclear data for hafnium isotopes in neutron transport applications. These experiments are part of the ICSBEP and were designed to assess the effect of hafnium cross sections on system reactivity across a range of neutron energy spectra.

The benchmark configurations involve critical assemblies composed of HEU metal plates moderated with polyethylene, with hafnium plates inserted into specific locations within the core for moderation and a ring of hafnium for reflection. The polyethylene moderator plates include various thicknesses, and the hafnium is present as either natural or isotopically representative metal plates. The experimental setups were selected to span thermal, intermediate, and fast neutron energy regimes, allowing for detailed sensitivity studies of resolved and unresolved resonance behavior.

Each case in the TEX-Hf benchmark is associated with a specific average lethargy causing fission, which helps characterize the neutron spectrum of the system. Sensitivity profiles generated using TSUNAMI confirm that these benchmarks are highly responsive to the capture and total cross sections of hafnium, especially ^{177}Hf .

In total, seven benchmark configurations were analyzed in this study, with average fission lethargies ranging from approximately 4 eV to over 350 keV. This range ensures that the evaluation of hafnium cross sections is tested comprehensively against realistic reactor-relevant conditions. The seven benchmark configurations used in this study, as documented in the ICSBEP benchmark repository, are summarized in Table III. The table lists the ICSBEP benchmark identifiers with the corresponding energy of average lethargy causing fission (EALF). The sensitivities of k_{eff} to the capture cross section for the seven benchmarks are shown in Figure 4, which illustrates how variations in the capture data influence the calculated reactivity across different neutron energy spectra.

Table III. Seven critical experiments sensitive to the hafnium cross sections.

Benchmark ID	EALF (eV)
HEU-MET-THERM-037-005	3.82
HEU-MET-MIXED-022-004	88.65
HEU-MET-INTER-013-003	930.06
HEU-MET-INTER-013-006	1178.60
HEU-MET-INTER-013-002	6097.69
HEU-MET-FAST-105-001	1.22×10^5
HEU-MET-FAST-105-007	3.51×10^5

 Figure 4. Sensitivities of k_{eff} to the ^{177}Hf capture cross section for the seven benchmarks.

4. RESULTS

To assess the performance of the new ^{177}Hf resonance evaluation, cross section libraries were processed with AMPX for use in the SCALE/KENO continuous-energy Monte Carlo code. Benchmark calculations were performed for the seven TEX-Hf configurations documented in the ICSBEP Handbook. The KENO Monte Carlo calculations were performed with a statistical uncertainty of approximately 10 pcm. The experiments span thermal, intermediate, and fast neutron spectra, with EALF values ranging from approximately 4 eV to over 350 keV, providing broad coverage of reactor-relevant conditions.

Table IV summarizes the calculated C/E values obtained using ENDF/B-VIII.1 and the new evaluation.

The comparison highlights the effect of the updated resonance parameters on system reactivity. Compared with ENDF/B-VIII.1, the new evaluation shows a slight improvement in the k_{eff} results, mainly for benchmarks with EALF values below 1 keV. This improvement reflects the better description of the resolved resonance region provided by the updated parameters, which has the greatest effect in thermal and epithermal spectra. For benchmarks with higher EALF values, the results obtained with the new evaluation are generally consistent with those from ENDF/B-VIII.1. This consistency was expected because the higher-energy portion of the library was retained from the reference evaluation. These findings highlight the importance of accurate resonance data for applications that involve thermal and intermediate spectra and confirm the robustness of the existing evaluation in the fast energy range. Future work will extend the analysis into the unresolved resonance region, incorporate additional integral benchmarks, and perform uncertainty quantification to more fully assess the effect of the new evaluation on practical applications. Although the differences in C/E values are small and mostly within 1σ experimental uncertainties, the consistent trend toward improved agreement for low-EALF benchmarks indicates a better representation of the resonance region. A more rigorous treatment of propagated uncertainty is planned as part of future work.

Table IV. Comparison of calculated C/E values for the seven TEX-Hf benchmark cases using ENDF/B-VIII.1 and the new ^{177}Hf evaluation. Experimental benchmark values are included for reference.

Benchmark ID	Experiment	New ^{177}Hf Evaluation	ENDF/B-VIII.1
HEU-MET-THERM-037-005	1.00177 ± 0.00147	1.001925	1.002047
HEU-MET-MIXED-022-004	0.99843 ± 0.00124	1.001833	1.002369
HEU-MET-INTER-013-003	0.99936 ± 0.00154	1.002063	1.002558
HEU-MET-INTER-013-006	0.99943 ± 0.00142	1.002031	1.002622
HEU-MET-INTER-013-002	0.99908 ± 0.00158	1.002379	1.002909
HEU-MET-FAST-105-001	0.99903 ± 0.00147	1.001969	1.001723
HEU-MET-FAST-105-007	0.99943 ± 0.00137	0.999448	0.999648

The sensitivities of k_{eff} to the capture cross section, shown in Figure 4, confirm that the TEX-Hf benchmarks are strongly influenced by hafnium resonance behavior, especially for ^{177}Hf . This makes them particularly valuable for testing the accuracy of evaluated data in both the resolved and unresolved resonance regions. These results demonstrate the value of the TEX-Hf benchmark series as an integral validation tool for hafnium nuclear data. Although differential measurements provide detailed information on individual resonance parameters, the TEX-Hf cases ensure that evaluated cross sections reproduce criticality behavior in realistic reactor-relevant configurations. Because hafnium is widely used in control materials and structural components, validation against these benchmarks directly supports applications in reactor physics, criticality safety, and advanced system design. In future work, comparisons of the new ^{177}Hf resonance evaluation with existing libraries such as JENDL-5 and JEFF-4.0 will help quantify improvements and identify remaining gaps in hafnium nuclear data.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A preliminary resonance evaluation of ^{177}Hf was performed in the energy range from 10^{-5} eV to 1 keV using the SAMMY R-matrix code. The updated parameters were incorporated into the JEFF-4.0 template and processed with AMPX to produce cross section libraries suitable for SCALE/KENO continuous-energy calculations. Benchmark testing was performed with the TEX-Hf series from the ICSBEP Handbook, which provides integral validation over thermal, epithermal, and fast neutron spectra.

Compared with ENDF/B-VIII.1, the new evaluation yields improved agreement with experimental k_{eff} results, particularly for benchmarks with EALF values below 1 keV, where resonance behavior domi-

nates. In the intermediate and fast ranges, the results remain consistent with ENDF/B-VIII.1, reflecting the robustness of the higher-energy portions of the reference evaluation. These findings confirm the importance of accurate resonance data for reactor-relevant applications that involve hafnium, especially in systems where hafnium is used as a structural or control material.

Future work will extend the evaluation into the unresolved resonance region, incorporate additional integral benchmarks, and include uncertainty quantification. Together, these steps will further strengthen the reliability of hafnium nuclear data for applications in reactor physics, criticality safety, and advanced system design.

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